

Exposure to sharp injuries among hospital medical waste handlers

Ahmed Lateef Alkhaqani^{1*}

¹Ministry of health, Al-Najaf Direction, Al-Sadder Medical Hospital, Najaf 00964, Iraq.

*Corresponding to: Ahmed Lateef Alkhaqani. Ministry of Health, Al-Najaf Direction, Al-Sadder Medical Hospital, Alwaali Street, Najaf 00964, Iraq. E-mail: ahmedl.alkhaqani@student.uokufa.edu.iq.

Dear editor

Health care workers are generally predisposed to injuries from sharps as a health hazard. This is more pronounced among waste handlers. Exposure to medical waste in hospitals and health facilities results in injuries and contagious diseases. Therefore, health workers, including nurses, doctors, technicians, and hospital cleaning workers, are always alerted to exercise the utmost caution and not to be exposed to the waste produced by the patient, especially through cuts or scrapes from the patient's sharp injuries, touching or inhalation or exposure to spills or splashes of liquids from medical waste or any waste resulting from patient care or contact with his body fluids [1].

Clinical or healthcare wastes, comprising the detritus of human or veterinary healthcare, are highly variable in composition. A substantial proportion may comprise relatively innocuous packaging and other non-hazardous materials, though some fractions may be contaminated with blood or body fluids that may contain potentially harmful microorganisms. Cross-contamination renders the entire load potentially harmful to health. Though blood-borne virus transmission is the foremost risk, the literature records a substantial list of pathogens causing infection following accidental exposure to blood and body fluids. Sharps or 'needle-stick' injury, a cut or puncture wound resulting in skin penetration by a hypodermic needle, surgical blade, fragment of glass or metal, or other sharp items, including rigid plastic, is the primary hazard for those working with healthcare wastes. Though much attention is paid to the safety of healthcare workers and their protection from sharps injury, the welfare and safety of those in the waste disposal sector have received very little attention. No report exists to define the incidence of sharps injuries to this key worker group. All sharp items capable of causing the injury must be discarded into robust, tamper-proof, puncture-resistant containers [2].

Health workers in the field of hygiene, who are in direct contact with medical waste from the collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal, are more susceptible to infectious injuries resulting from medical waste. They are more vulnerable to cases of pricking, scratching, and cutting the skin with needles, scalpels, and sharp materials contaminated with patient fluids [3]. Sharp injury can occur whenever a worker is exposed to contact with a sharp tool, which may result in harm. Sharps and needle-stick injuries are wounds caused by needles and other sharp medical instruments (e.g., scalpel, blades, and scissors) that accidentally puncture or cut the skin. Sharps and needles may only cause small wounds in the skin, but the effects can be worse. Such instruments come in contact with blood and other body fluids and may carry the risk of infections. If a contaminated device punctures the skin of healthcare workers (HCWs), they face a high risk of occupational exposure to infected, hazardous fluids [4]. Sharps injuries in healthcare waste handlers occur mainly to the hands due to lifting plastic bags containing needles without covers (Figure 1).

If hospital waste is not managed properly, it is proven to be harmful to the environment. It poses a threat not only to the employees working in the hospital but also to the people in the surrounding area. Infectious waste may be associated with diseases like viral hepatitis and other life-threatening viral infections, as well as pyogenic and enteric infections. The reuse of syringes and other used items from waste can transmit disease and has a significant impact on public

health. Therefore, hospital staff should properly dispose of syringes and other used equipment and supplies, if necessary, cutting needles of syringes so that the needle cannot be reused. In addition to properly disposing of syringes, hospitals should adopt procedures and policies to manage the waste generated correctly. There should be an emphasis on all stages, from generation to final treatment and disposal of the waste through the establishment of source separation, sound sanitary collection, and storage of medical wastes, ensuring transportation with approved packaging, the treatment of wastes by safe and environmentally-sound methods and disposal of final residues in confined and carefully-designed sites [5].

In Iraq, waste handling is carried out by hospital cleaning workers employed by the hospitals. They collect medical waste from different departments and transport it manually to temporary storage areas. Methods including incineration, burial, dumping, and removal in municipal bins are employed for the disposal of wastes in all hospitals. Though much attention is paid to the safety of health professionals and their protection from sharps injuries and bloodstained body fluids exposure, the welfare and safety of non-health professionals working in the collection, transport, and disposal of wastes has received very little attention. No reports exist defining the incidence of sharps injuries, bloodstained body fluids exposure, and infection rates following accidents in these key working groups in Iraq. This article highlights and discusses a specific point, which exposes hospital cleaning workers to accidents, cuts, and scratches on the skin by sharp tools that may be contaminated with the blood and body fluids of the patient, an attempt to understand the method and reasons behind the occurrence of such accidents and the search for defects in the management of medical waste that led to the presence of such injuries are in hospital cleaner workers.

Few and limited studies have discussed the exposure of hospital cleaning workers to accidents and skin scratches by sharp tools that may be contaminated with the patient's blood and body fluids, including the Ethiopian study by Shiferaw Y, et al., (2012) reported

Figure 1 Body sites most vulnerable to needle-sticks and sharp injuries in medical waste handlers (fingers, hands, and sides of the leg) [1].

that hospital cleaner workers were exposed to needle-stick from one to two cases by 42.1% and 67.5% of patients' body blood and fluids. The study found that all the studied groups were not immunized against hepatitis B because of the financial cost that these poor workers cannot cover and the lack of a free virus vaccination program by the state for citizens. The study also confirmed that about 50% of hospital cleaning workers do not wear gloves or shoes during work. It is also confirmed that their information about the seriousness of the disease caused by hepatitis viruses is very simple. However, most of them are well acquainted with the immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and its seriousness. The study also confirmed that the risks of exposure to blood, patient's body fluids, and needle sticks are very high among hospital cleaning workers and local authorities should develop a proper medical waste management program [5].

A study conducted by Blenkarn JI & Odd C, (2008) dealt with needle-stick incidents in hospital cleaning workers and calculated the incidence rate of 40 needle-stick incidents documented in the group studied with a percentage of one case in 29,000 working hours [2]. Six cases of injuries were due to injection needles sticking from the overfilled sharps boxes or containers that are not hermetically sealed and 34 cases were due to the presence of needles and plastic garbage bags designated for medical waste. In most cases, injuries occurred on the fingers or the hand. The study noticed that most workers do not prefer heavy gloves that can withstand needles because they are annoying to deal with when transporting the waste, so they resort to light plastic gloves that do not withstand the stick of needles. Also, it is necessary to conduct the separation of hazardous waste from household waste, as this procedure contributes to and reduces needle-stick injuries. One of the major mistakes and neglect is throwing needles and syringes in plastic bags, as this behavior is the major reason workers have a needle.

A study by Olaitan PB, et al., (2012) included 43 hospital cleaning workers who deal with medical waste [6]. It was through personal interviews with them that they were asked questions about this profession and whether they were trained on how to deal with hospital waste, poor serious infectious waste, acute waste, or waste similar to household waste, as well as whether they were exposed to needle and sharp materials through their daily work. The results were as follows: twenty-eight male and female workers (65.8%) had been trained on this job before they took up employment, while (32.5%) had not been trained at all for this job and did not know the magnitude of the risks they deal with. Only 31 workers (90.7%) consistently use gloves before transporting and collecting medical waste. Only three of the workers (7.0%) had medical tests to detect hepatitis B virus (HBV), and 19 workers (44.2%) took tests to detect the HIV, while 10 workers (23.3%) conducted tests for three viruses (HBV, HCV, HIV). As for their exposure to acupuncture, 11 workers (25.6%) were exposed to needles and the fingers, while 7 (93%) were the most frequent places where acupuncture occurred.

Occupational exposure to needle-stick injuries and sharp injuries continues to have a major health problem in the healthcare systems of developing countries. Needle-stick and sharp injuries are critical occupational hazards for healthcare workers. Globally, it is estimated that out of the total of 35 million HCWs worldwide, 3 million experience needle-stick injuries every year; hospital cleaning workers are at the greatest risk, with up to 40% of all needle-stick injuries. Exposure to medical waste in hospitals and health facilities results in injuries and contagious diseases. Therefore, health workers, including nurses, doctors, technicians, and clean workers, are always alerted to exercise the utmost caution and not to be exposed to the waste produced by the patient, especially through cuts or scrapes from the patient's sharp injuries, touching or inhalation, exposure to spills or splashes. This is more pronounced among waste handlers.

Both local and international government authorities and concerned bodies in collaboration with other private sectors should take action such as training on safety and standard precautions to reduce the risk of needle-stick or sharp injuries and promote the health of HCWs in different occupational settings of healthcare systems. Planning systematic educational programs targeted at using personal protective

equipment and refreshing training programs to promote good safety practices. Stressing the importance of reporting needle-stick or sharp injury incidents and developing a defined system aimed at registering needle stick and sharps injuries to achieve higher safety. Development of safety management systems and training on workplace safety [7]. In addition, training and re-training HCWs are important and should be encouraged. All health workers should have pre-employment immunization against hepatitis B, C, and others before commencing their jobs. Workers should be screened for infectious diseases that can be of legal problem while on the job and the workers should be effectively immunized, implementation a sorting system of the medical waste from the household. Develop a national program for immunizations and vaccinations for all workers, especially hospital cleaning workers. It is necessary to detect and examine hygiene workers periodically and continuously for infectious diseases to avoid transmission of infection to others and treat the disease before it aggravates. All sharp tools that cause injuries should be discarded in sturdy, tamper-resistant, puncture-resistant containers.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

HCWs, healthcare workers; HIV, immunodeficiency virus; HBV, hepatitis B virus.

Citation

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